

Master Thesis on Sound & Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Expressive Performance Modeling in Polyphonic Flamenco and Jazz Guitar

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Supervisor: Sergio Giraldo

Co-Supervisor: Rafael Ramírez

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Abstract

In musical performances, expressive models have been proposed in order to study the analysis and characterization of the deviations that a musician introduces when performing a musical piece. In this work, expressiveness in guitar performance is presented as a case of study. However, in guitar case studies, the ability to produce polyphonic sounds and its musical versatility, results on a variability of sounds, possessing significant challenges on the automatic transcription and on the analysis of the recorded data when building the dataset for the model. Data-driven methods have become increasingly popular in order to approach problems like guitar transcription and, datasets of labeled audio data are highly needed. This work proposes a system capable of collecting audio and MIDI annotations from guitar performances based on specific musical pieces, jazz and flamenco in this work. In particular, by recording guitar performances using a hexaphonic pickup, the system is able to, not only provide recording of the individual strings, but also to largely automate the annotation process of the expressive content of the music performance. Then a pretrained machine learning model is used in order to automatically generate music sequence excerpts based on the acquired data. Finally, different sets of data are presented in order to compare results and qualitative evaluations of the generated sequences are performed.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The data acquisition processes for expressiveness modeling systems, that are focused on music performances, can be time-consuming regarding the processing and the amount of data involved, therefore, data is not taken and models are not built. Due to this lack of data, in some cases, only well-know music styles and performances are considered in these studies, regardless of the potential knowledge of minority music styles.

Automatic data acquisition systems have been considered in order to tackle this scenario, but some kind of pre or post processing is needed, thus, the process could not be as directly as desired. However, trying to build a complete straightforward automatic data acquisition system could be rather difficult and even impossible under some specific circumstances.

As mentioned before, this work is also focused on the use of the acquired data in order to use it for modeling expressiveness in music performances and the generation of new music sequences based on the built model. Previous knowledge of the specific selected music style is required, and different music styles require different modeling approaches. Regarding expressiveness modeling systems for music performances, recent advanced techniques on Artificial Intelligence have considerably improve the

results and, therefore, the field of automatic generation of expressive music have been improved the results as well.

On the other hand, this work emphasizes on the real-time interaction with the resulting model, providing a tool that helps music creativity processes. The tool consists of a web site that provides an automatic generated sequence based on the data acquired and a sequence input by the user. Several methods are implemented to provide the input sequence of the user: created by an interactive MIDI panel, by uploading a MIDI file or by recording directly in the web using an external MIDI device.

The presented work is based on past researches conducted in the Music Technology Group from Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Barcelona), in particular those research that tackle guitar transcription using a hexaphonic MIDI pickup and those that tackle flamenco music style. Regarding the automatic music generation models, this work has been inspired by the recent researches done by Magenta on automatic music generation and on the tools that Magenta community develop in order to interact with the resulting models.

Considering these aspects, two different fields have been tackled in this work. On the one hand, the process and the building of a new dataset for posterior studying and modeling of specific aspects of the data acquired, in this case, taking into account the expressiveness involved in each style, jazz or flamenco. Moreover, related to this, automatic generation based on the built model is also tackled in this work. On the other hand, the work has been focused on the implementation of an interactive web application based on multimodal technologies.

1.2 Problem Definition

The aim of this project is to contribute on the acquisition process of polyphonic guitar music performance expressiveness for the later implementation of automatic generative polyphonic music expressiveness sequences focused on flamenco style. In addition, another important aspect is the collaboration in the area of music

computing interactivity and music production. Knowing that, the project should take into account several aspects: the data acquisition system, the actual building of the model, and the deployment and interactivity of it on a web site. Thus, the primary objective of this project is to acquire the dataset using a straightforward and non-intrusive method for a specific polyphonic music style performed by a guitar. The data must be acquired cleanly enough so that neither the modelling nor the expressiveness of the performance appear distorted and no preprocessing of the acquired data is needed.

Moreover, the research of this implementations is focused on building a simple an interactive interface; knowing that some stakeholders might not be familiar with interactive system. We work on two different sets of data processed and managed accordingly in order to provide wider and reliable results.

Taking into consideration that, other works offer similar and interesting approaches but few of them focused on specific music styles like flamenco. Moreover, flamenco MIDI guitar datasets that include expressiveness information have not been widely researched. On the other hand, Magenta project worked on several music generation models, one of them is PerformanceRNN. This work is based on PerformanceRNN to automatically generate expressive music sequence excerpts based on the data acquired from the music performances.

The data acquisition system and the interactive interface proposed, should not imply a loss of interactivity, nor a consequent contamination of the data obtained.

As shown in the figure 1, several tasks must be achieved by this project:

- **Data acquisition:** Study and recognition of the best data acquisition approach for the proposed project; how this approach could affect the performance and the contamination of the data, analyze pros and cons, e.g. Polyphony or latency.
- **Data Cleaning:** In case of contamination of the data due to the data acquisition approach, apply signal processing algorithms in order to correct it.

Figure 1: Diagram framework representation of the proposed system.

- Dataset building: Creation, organization and management of datasets considering the final objective of the project. A specific structure of the data could help the future retrieval of it and even optimize some processes.
- Build the model: Make use of the acquired data to create a model capable of generating new sequences taking into consideration expressiveness aspects.
- Tune the model: Being able to change specific parameters when training the model in order to accurately get the expected results.
- Deployment of the model: Integration of the trained model in a web site to allow the users the possibility of interacting with it.

- **Interactive System:** Development of an interactive system capable of generating input sequences valid for the trained model. The system should also be able to run the model with the given inputs and retrieve the generated sequence from the model.
- **Input of the interactive system:** Implementation of different inputs methods. The user should be able to interact with the web interface and several inputs methods for the model are proposed.

Taking into account the mentioned tasks, the system proposed in this project should solve:

- Straightforward acquisition of polyphonic guitar performance data.
- Acquisition of not contaminated data using a hexaphonic MIDI guitar pickup.
- Acquisition of guitar performance data suitable for training a pretrained model.
- Real-time webpage interactivity with a trained model for the generation of expressiveness sequences (POSTPONED).
- Real-time interactivity in order to generate (or route) the inputs through the webpage.
- Real-time reviewing of the output of the model using the same webpage (POSTPONED).

1.3 Scientific Context

As it has been already observed, the proposed project is involved in several frameworks or fields, but mainly focused on data acquisition and artificial intelligence. Some of the areas are between these two topics and could overlap each other. Regarding the user interaction part, user experience field should be taken into account too, since the final result of the project involve the user interaction and perception of the systems and the generated results.

Specifically, regarding Artificial Intelligence, the project is involved on the field of automatic sequence generation, making use of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). In addition, web integration should also be considered by addressing the integration of trained models into a website environment and the study of its interaction.

1.4 Contributions

As already seen, different fields are involved, and many research topics are covered in this project. The following list summarize the principal contributions and stakeholders.

- Automatically data acquisition:
 - Straightforward acquisition methods in order to retrieve expressiveness data of polyphonic guitar performances.
- Modeling acquired data:
 - Make use of the acquired data to retrain a pretrained model.
 - Automatic generation of audio excerpts based on the model trained.
- App development:
 - Analysis and implementation of basic principles of perception and user experience in order to development the web application, taking into account non-expertise music/technology profiles.
 - Implementation of a web application capable of interact (input generation or input routing) and retrieve music sequence excerpts based on an uploaded trained model.

1.5 Outline of the Dissertation

The outline of this dissertation is organized as follows.

In chapter 2 we present the most important aspects that constitute the actual state-of-the-art of the music transcription systems. It also explores the different types of transcriptions that can be found and it finally focuses on polyphonic performances of the guitar instrument as a case of study. It explores the different approaches that have been used in the past and how these approaches relate with the acquisition of expressiveness information of guitar performances.

In chapter 3 we present the materials, methods and functions of the proposed system. The general framework is detailed and divided into its main parts. The different libraries and additional software are also discussed. Finally, the built dataset is described.

Chapter 4 presents the system-wide operation, expanding the entire diagram detailed before and explaining in detail the methods, functions and implementations. It focuses on the recording system, on the modeling of the data and on the web application.

Chapter 5 gives a summary of the research presented, commenting the results obtained. Focusing on the generated sequences by the model and on the surveys related with the qualitative analysis of them.

Finally, chapter 6 presents the conclusions about the research done. It mainly discusses the reliability of the obtained results on the qualitative tests. Chapter 6 also contains the related access for the repositories and the discussion about future directions.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Music Transcription

Several scientific advances permit us to address now, successfully, to the complex problem of Automatic Music Transcription (AMT) and signal processing techniques and machine learning approaches have contributed on the state of the art, boosting various aspects of the music transcription. Music transcription refers to "the analysis of an acoustic musical signal so as to write down the pitch, onset time, duration, and source of each sound that occurs in it", [1]. Traditional music transcription approaches uses note symbols in order to indicate the parameters in a music piece. On the other hand, other modern approaches of music transcription exists and they are researched, for example, in modern guitar transcriptions, the use of tablatures (Tabs) [2]. Regarding computational transcription systems, MIDI files format [3] are widely used and standardized as an appropriated format for music notation. A common thing to all these representations is that they capture musically meaningful parameters that can be used when performing or when synthesizing the music piece in question.

Therefore, in order to capture those musically meaningful parameters, the process of transcribe audio music into music notation involves the study of music perception (complex auditory scenes) [1], cognition (musical recognition), knowledge represen-

tation and inference [4]. Regarding the study of the music perception, in Western music theory, the main constituent music elements which are often distinguished are melody, harmony, rhythm and timbre. In 1993, Gardner [5] proposes that the main elements of music are pitch, rhythm and timbre, and pitch is constituent for melody and harmony.

Apart from these categories, i.e. melody, harmony, rhythm and timbre, used in traditional approaches in Western music theory, dynamics and expressiveness are often considered essential conditions for music information retrieval systems. Properties of these music elements can be defined using level descriptors. Level descriptors are typically categorized in three groups:

- Low-level descriptors: Define acoustic and sensory properties of the audio signal. These descriptors are retrieved from frame-based analysis of an acoustic wave.
- Mid-level descriptors: Involve time-space transformations and context dependencies within specific time frame. Time-space transformations define the musical signal content in spatial terms and in temporal terms. For example: timbre and chords (spatial) or beat and meter (temporal). Based on Lesafre [6] content formation take into account a time frame of maximum three seconds.
- High-level descriptors: Involve learning and categorization beyond the representation. They are related to cognitive, expressiveness and emotions.

Above-mentioned characteristics and approaches are necessary when the transcription process is taking place and they are crucial when researching on automatic music transcriptions tasks.

2.1.1 Automatic Music Transcription

Automatic music transcription (AMT) approaches (i.e., computational algorithms that convert acoustic music signals into music notation automatically) comprises

several complex subtasks in signal processing. These subtasks may include multipitch estimation, onset and offset detection, instrument recognition, beat and rhythm tracking, interpretation of expressive timing and dynamics, and score typesetting [4]. Due to the complexity and the number of subtasks that AMT involves is considered a fundamental problem in signal processing and music information retrieval (MIR) fields [7]. For these reasons AMT is considered a challenging and an open problem in the literature, in particular for polyphonic music (simultaneous notes) and multi-instrumental.

In the 1970s Moorer proposed first attempts on transcribing polyphonic music automatically. In [8] Moorer proposed a system capable of transcribe two-voices compositions. Since the beginning of the 1990s, AMT trends focused on statistical methods with successfully results. On the other hand, recent approaches include some of the above-mentioned traditional signal processing methods [9] [10], probabilistic models, non-negative matrix factorization and neural networks.

Figure 2: Main sources of information in music transcription, from *Signal Processing Methods for Music Transcription*, Klapuri [1]

2.1.2 Monophonic and Polyphonic Transcription

When approaching automatic music transcription the main distinctive fact to consider is the number of voices that the system could get. When there is only one

voice plying at each time, the task is treated as a monophonic transcription task. When several voices take place at the same time, simultaneously, the task is considered a polyphonic transcription task. Therefore, monophonic music sources are those capable of producing only one single sound at each time (e.g. Sax or flute). On the other hand, polyphonic music sources (e.g. Guitar or piano) are capable of playing several sounds (notes) at each time, in the case of guitar instrument, due to the independent strings.

Development of techniques for monophonic pitch detection has received particular attention, monophonic AMT is considered a solved problem compared with polyphonic transcription. Remarkable early works in monophonic transcription are the ones by Rabiner [11]. In polyphonic music transcription two or more concurrent sounds may contain partials which share the same frequency values and partials overlapping could occur, the complexity of the spectral content increases as the number of concurrent voices increase.

2.1.3 Automatic Guitar Transcription

When approaching automatic guitar music transcription, in this work, we are addressing a polyphonic transcription problem. The polyphony is caused by the different guitar strings as each one is considered a monophonic music source. During guitar performances, chords or two simultaneous strings can generate polyphony.

When dealing with polyphonic music, estimating the fundamental frequency is considered a notorious difficult task in music information retrieval field. Recently related works are focused on deep learning models but historically, most of the algorithms for estimating fundamental frequencies in polyphonic music were based on heuristics. For example, enforcing spectral smoothness and emphasizing harmonic content [12], comparing properties spectral peaks/non-peaks regions [13] or combining time and frequency-domain periodicities [10]. Gradually, more machine learning approaches have been proposed for example; hidden Markov models (HMMs), non-negative matrix factorization, support vector machines (SVM) or recurrent neural networks (RNN).

Other approaches focused, directly, on produce the fingering and chords of a guitar performance instead of the notes or tablature. Barbancho [14], applied HMMs and propose a method for extracting the fingering configurations automatically from a recorded guitar performance. Humphrey and Bello [15] tackle the problem by using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), in order to transcribe a guitar tablature from audio, the dataset used was pop music recordings instead of isolated guitar excerpts. Video approaches where used by Hrybyk and Kim in order to recognize guitar chords [16].

Deep learning approaches using CNN have shown promise results for automatic music transcriptions tasks. Proposed work by Stigita [17] focuses on hybrid neural network model for piano transcription that combines CNN and RNN. Recently, Wiggins and Kim presented a CNN model [18] capable of learning a mapping directly from audio data in order to create its tablature. The network trained and tested uses microphone recordings from the GuitarSet dataset, achieving the state-of-the-art of multipitch estimation algorithm in guitar instrument. GuitarSet by Xi [19] evaluated the Deep Saliency multiple-f0 work from [20]. The GuitarSet annotated dataset is available as an open resource and has been largely used by the research community.

2.2 Hexaphonic Pickup Approach

In order to approach the absence of realistic (expressive) annotated guitar recordings the hexaphonic pickup outputs one channel of audio signal per guitar string and custom annotations. This process facilitates the acquisition, transcription and further analysis of guitar recordings, and solves the problem of the absence of realistic polyphonic annotated complex guitar recordings taking into account expressiveness (e.g., energy performance actions).

First approaches of collecting data using an hexaphonic guitar pickup was proposed by O'Grady and Rickard in 2009 [21], the string signals are analyzed by using supervised non-negative matrix factorization. Other research that used hexaphonic

pickups presents techniques for the analysis and synthesis [22] or have been used for visualizing guitar performances [23]. The GuitarSet project, above-mentioned, made use of an hexaphonic pickup in order to retrieve the annotated data and created the dataset. Regarding recent works, in [24], Senvaityte made use of the hexaphonic guitar dataset (GuitarSet) in order to approach the separation task between strings using non-negative matrix factorization and factor deconvolution. Most of the researches done recently, that are involved with an hexaphonic guitar pickup, are based on the GuitarSet dataset due to the high quality guitar recordings alongside rich annotations and metadata.

2.3 Expressiveness in Music Performances

Expressiveness in music is defined as the manipulations that the performer does in duration, onset, energy and ornamentation. Some of these manipulations can be stipulated on the score but most of them succeeded as a Performance Actions (PA). PA are not usually indicated at the score of the musical piece and gives to the performance an unique and personal expression from the artist. PA mostly appeared unconsciously and may vary in duration, timbre, pitch and energy. First relevant work is presented in 2001 by Juslin and Sloboda [25].

Lately, music expression studies have been mostly focused on machine learning based systems, but early researches have been involved on rule-based systems. This systems are based on the work of Gabrielsson in 1985, that it is defined as an analysis-by-synthesis system. An important example is the KTH model, see [26] where the performance is shaped by a linear combination of the effects of the rules, which the user can weight individually.

Data-driven approaches, relying on machine learning, represent a significant trend when dealing with performance expression modeling. Those systems have been used to infer score-performance mappings from large collection of real data. In contrast of rule-based approaches where performances rules (expressiveness) are manually annotated based on music expertise. In [27] Cancino-Chacón overview the methods

and exposes a comprehensive work tackling future research directions to advance the field.

Early data-driven approaches achieved successful results at learning explicit performance expression rules, but on the other hand, instance-based methods and recent advances in machine learning have become more relevant in computational performance modeling. The use of computational models have been involved in several purposes, Cancino-Chacón [27] present a taxonomy of different data-driven methods for analysis and generation of expressive performances, the work also includes several tables that summarize researches grouped by section.

In figure 3 different categories are presented. In this work we emphasize those methods that study and analyze performances and those that are related to performance generation too. The proposed work focuses mostly on the performance generation and we do not take into account specific expressiveness features of a specific style. We do consider expressiveness features that we might find in a music sequence, but we do not model the feature itself, but modeled sequences containing these features (because we were able to acquire them).

Performance analysis methods can be categorized in two groups; methods that explain or model aspects of the performances and, on the other side, methods that compare different expressive performances.

Regarding the first group, several works focused on dynamics and expressive dynamics, Kosta [28]. On the other hand, other works research on different score descriptors as pitch, metrics, dynamics and timing [27]. Machine learning approaches and feature selections methods, allow Giraldo [29] and Bantula [30] to evaluate a number of score descriptors in modeling expressive performance actions for jazz guitar and jazz ensembles.

On the other hand, methods that rely on comparing expressive performances are based on the differences found when comparing the same piece but performed by different musicians. This approach allows to study the commonalities and differences in performances strategies. Different metrics are proposed by Sapp [31] for

Figure 3: Proposed taxonomy presented by Cancino-Chacón in *Computational Models of Expressive Music Performance: A Comprehensive and Critical Review*, [27]

comparing collections of performances of the same score. In [32] metrics retrieved from performances are used in order to extract individual performance styles in violinists. Similar works researches on different instruments, e.g. saxophone [33].

The captured features from performances usually rely on small local contexts, exposed results are not properly taking into account long term time dependencies when analyzing or generating performances. Work researched by Widmer in 2017 [34] presented advances in deep learning and open some probabilities in order to deal with the mentioned complexities. Recently researches from Magenta (e.g. MusicVAE [35]) imply relevant advances in the music generation and music expressiveness

fields. In [36], groove expression in drum excerpts are studied and developed with successful and relevant results. Taking into account the guitar instrument as a source of sound, several researches worked on expressiveness, Siquier [37], where hexaphonic pickup is used in order to retrieve guitar information. Giraldo S. and Ramírez R. [38] presented an approach for modeling jazz guitar performances which allows to describe not only dynamics and timing, but also ornamentation.

Chapter 3

Materials & Methods

In the previous section we presented and discussed about the recent advances in technology to deal with data acquisition and automatic music generation in guitar music expressive performances. Moreover, the discussed scenario presents a robust and advanced AI techniques that are in continue developing providing new contributions to the different involved fields of this project.

A key point considered in this project is the straightforward and simplicity of building a dataset of guitar performances to later build a model with the acquired data considering expressiveness information. As it has been cited previously, datasets of guitar performances are well-known, but they are usually focused on wider music styles like pop, classic or jazz. Of course, minority music styles dataset can be found but not as easy as the mentioned ones.

As expected, the proposed data acquisition system, the hexaphonic midi pickup, besides the straightforwardness commented before, the system should not be intrusive during the performance but nevertheless, the restriction of working preferably on electric guitar could be a limitation for some styles like the main one proposed for this work, flamenco. Even thought, both parts of the proposed project, the interactive web page and the acquisition of the guitar performance data are focused to be simple, straightforward and intuitively.

The complexity of the data acquisition system, the intrusiveness, the real-time response of the system and the real time response of the web page interaction are the main parameters to highlight on this project. Other projects are related with other approaches where the data used is already available and processed or on the other hand, the data should be acquired but can be time-consuming regarding the post processes that are involved in order to clean the data.

In this work we are referring to "Non-intrusiveness" to the alteration of the personal relationship between the instrument, the guitar in this case, and the performer, so physical additions that changes guitar weight or balance or playability could denature musician performances.

This chapter is divided into Frameworks, Libraries and Dataset. During the first section of the chapter an overview of the different frameworks used is detailed. Then a review of the programming libraries used is presented and finally, the structure of the dataset is explained.

3.1 Framework

Following the explanations exposed above, the framework of the proposed project can be divided into three main parts: *Data Acquisition*, *Modeling the Data* and *Web Application Interface*.

3.1.1 Data Acquisition

The most common way to convert guitar signal to MIDI is using a MIDI pickup. This is an external pickup that is mount onto the electric guitar and is completely separate from "normal pickups". As mentioned before, the MIDI pickup is the core system of the acquisition of guitar performance data for the presented project. Through this methodology, the acquired information is straightforward retrieved and expressiveness information is also obtained.

The way MIDI pickups work is they capture each individual vibration of the strings and sends that information separately to a decoder. The decoder will then convert

that information into MIDI. The pickup is mounted between the bridge and the bridge pickup. It is a divided pickup which means there are individual sensors under each string. The control unit could also be mounted onto the face of the guitar, see figure 4.

Figure 4: Control Unit and MIDI pickup installed on the guitar during the jazz recording session.

The MIDI pickup used is the TriplePlay Wireless MIDI Guitar Controller ¹. The used model includes wireless controller, hexaphonic pickup, and wireless USB receiver, mounting brackets and hardware, fast-charge power pack, and USB charging cable. The device works with industry standard DAWs and virtual instruments. Another relevant point regarding this device is the affordance and the simplicity when installing it on the electric guitar and can be easily removed too, the device is also considered the most affordable and easy-to-use guitar synth around.

In order to have a more comprehensive database, clean guitar line audio is recorded

¹<https://www.fishman.com/landing-page-tripleplay/tripleplay-wireless-guitar-controller/>

too. From the obtained MIDI, tablature information is retrieved. The interface used is a Focusrite Scarlett 2i2 3rd generation², this interface provides two inputs (line or XLR) and two outputs, adequate for the proposed project, see figure 5.

Figure 5: Setup of the data acquisition system.

Both, the direct guitar line audio and the MIDI input from the pickup are processed and recorded using a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW), in our case Logic Pro X version 10.5.0 is used. Logic Pro is a DAW and MIDI sequencer software application for the macOS platform. It is considered the second most popular DAW, after Ableton Live. Some of the interesting features regarding MIDI technology include; MIDI keyboards compatibility and control surfaces for input and processing and for MIDI output. It features real-time scoring in musical notation, supporting guitar tablature, chord abbreviations and drum notation. Advanced MIDI editing is possible, where velocity, pitch, pitch-bends, note length, humanize and precise note positioning are affected.

Regarding the recording process, two different channels are used for each type of signal. For guitar line audio signal an audio type channel is used. On the other hand, for the MIDI guitar pickup, an External MIDI channel is used. Due to the real-time scoring in musical notation, Logic Pro can deal with the automatically

²<https://focusrite.com/en/usb-audio-interface/scarlett/scarlett-2i2>

creation of precise guitar tablatures based on the signal from the hexaphonic guitar pickup. The transcription of the performance is built as a guitar tablature (see figure 9) considering the exact finger position executed during the performance. Therefore, the presented dataset for this project includes three different types of information for the same recorded performance; MIDI information, Audio signal information and tablature information (finger-position).

As mentioned before, electric guitars may not be always the best suitable instrument regarding the music style. For example, in flamenco music style, electric guitar is rarely used, so, other guitar types have been considered in order to achieve a more natural performance.

The main challenge when dealing with other types of guitars is the use of the MIDI guitar pickup, the pickup captures electric impulses that the vibration of the metallic string is doing during the performance. Moreover, the electromagnetic sensors that captures each string information are separated by a fixed space specific for electric guitars, see figure 6.

The discussed aspects; the use of metallic strings and the fixed space between the pickup sensors, difficult the versatility of the TriplePlay MIDI pickup on other types of guitar. Nevertheless, the following approaches have been tried:

- TriplePlay MIDI pickup on Electroacoustic guitar: The use of the MIDI pickup on an electroacoustic guitar is conditioned by the space between sensors. This type of guitars does not present any kind of difficulties regarding the use of metallic strings. Metallic guitar strings are suitable for electro-acoustic guitars, information can be retrieved by the MIDI pickup, but the reliability may not be as good as in electric guitars because of the wider space between strings, compared to electric guitar string spaces.
- TriplePlay MIDI pickup on Spanish guitars: The use of the MIDI pickup on a Spanish guitar is mainly conditioned by the type of strings used. Spanish guitars (and Flamenco guitars) use nylon strings, therefore the pickup is not able

Figure 6: Close-up view of the installed MIDI pickup. Space between strings is fixed and precisely defined for electric guitars.

to capture the guitar performance information. Nevertheless, a workaround has been tried, the use of small parts of strings attached on the nylon strings just where the MIDI pickup is placed. Using this approach, the signal is captured but, as in the above-commented approach, the space between strings is wider than electric guitars, therefore, the information retrieved will not be as reliable as the electric guitar approaches.

In both approaches, inaccuracies on the strings at the extremes have been found; using the standard tuning (E-A-D-G-B-E), high-E and low-E.

Besides the TriplePlay MIDI pickup approach, other devices have been identified that could achieve better results in nylon guitar scenarios. RMC acoustic pickups³ feature individual sensors for each string. The individual RMC sensors provide

³<https://stores.soundislandmusic.com/rmc-acoustic-system/>

exceptionally accurate MIDI tracking. The custom filtering in the preamp provided by the same company delivers more natural reproduction of a mono signal. The preamp also provides the ability to drive a polyphonic processor, guitar synth or MIDI converter.

The sensors are installed directly into the guitar bridge, the ensemble is usually done by a guitar luthier. Therefore, the sensors cannot be easily removed and use them in another guitar. Another disadvantage to consider is the cost of the product, the price for 6 sensors (one per string) is around 300\$. The preamp is sold as a separated item and costs around 400\$. The prices do not consider the ensemble of the system into the guitar.

Therefore, the TriplePlay MIDI pickup is considered the most suitable approach. Compared to similar systems, the cost is relatively inexpensive and the retrieved information is accurate enough, even though, somehow, the system is restricted to electric guitars only.

3.1.2 Modeling the Data

The implementation of the modelling of the data and the processing of it have been carried out in two specific frameworks. Libraries and specific programming topics are detailed in the following sections.

The implementation has been carried out mainly in local-hosted Jupyter notebooks frameworks and Google Colab (hosted Jupyter notebook service). A Jupyter notebook is a web-based interactive computational environment for creating Jupyter notebook documents. These documents can contain code, text, mathematics, plots and rich media; by default, Jupyter notebooks language is Python. In this case, most of the libraries and external modules required are installed locally. Nevertheless, computationally demanding tasks will not be executed in local-hosted Jupyter notebooks.

When dealing with demanding computational tasks, Google Colab is used. Google Colab is a free Jupyter notebook environment that runs in the cloud and stores

its notebooks on Google Drive, requires no setup to use and provides free access to computing resources including GPUs. Google Colab is well suited to machine learning and in this project Google Colab framework has been used when dealing with computationally demanding tasks because of the free online hosting and the available computing resources.

3.1.3 Web Interface

The web interface developed in this project refers to a webpage capable of interact with a user that is not necessarily familiarized with technology. The design is focused on simple and intuitive interactions. Some of the aspects of the design were inspired on already developed interfaces, like the ones developed by the Magenta project. Taking into account this, the design process of the system must also follow these guidelines.

The relationship between the structure of the program and the interaction with the program is closely related and reflects the importance between program sections. In fact, it is important to highlight the program flow and its relationship with the user, and how the data could be modified through the different paths.

In order to develop this webapp, two different environments or frameworks have been used. On the one hand, Glitch⁴ has been used to store and deploy the code. Glitch is a collaborative programming environment in the browser and deploy code in real time. No servers are needed, and the deployment setup is already configured when a new project is created. Moreover, Glitch offers a wide community where developers, coders, designers, artists activists, students and educators take place. Glitch focuses on being a friendly, accessible community; since its launch, over a million people have used the site to make web applications.

On the other hand, Visual Studio Code (VS Code) framework has been used to edit and debug the code. Glitch provides compatibility with VS Code, including real-time collaboration, code rewind and live previews.

⁴<https://glitch.com/>

See figure 7, the diagram representation of the detailed framework.

Figure 7: Diagram framework representation of the proposed system.

3.2 Libraries

As mentioned, the presented project is divided in three different parts; *the acquisition of the data, the modeling process of the data* and finally *the development of the web application interface*. For each part, specific software libraries have been chosen. The following section reviews the software libraries used and discusses about the selection of them, moreover, libraries considered but not used are also mentioned and reviewed.

3.2.1 Data Acquisition Libraries

During the acquisition of the data, most of the tasks are carried on without using external libraries, actually, the specific acquisition process it could have done without the use of libraries. Nevertheless, two external software libraries have been used in order to acquire more accurate data and to complete the dataset. In order to acquire

more accurate data, we made use of the official TriplePlay software, that provides tools for recording, editing and provides also a preset editor and mixing console with a bank of MIDI sounds.

For this project, TriplePlay's calibrating tool feature is used, it provides a fine-tune tool focused on the Sensitivity/Tuner area of the MIDI pickup. The sensitivity meters for each string, which are used to fine-tune TriplePlay's response, figure 8. One of the main objectives of this project is to be able to retrieve the information of the expressiveness of guitar performances. To obtain correctly the mentioned information, calibrating the sensitivity of the MIDI pickup will help to acquire a more precise information of the velocities, i.e., the expressiveness involved.

Figure 8: Sensitivity/Tuner Area, small box in the center of the interface. Sensitivity meters for each string, in order to fine-tune TriplePlay's response

The sensitivity area from TriplePlay software consists of:

- String name. Identifies each string by pitch (in standard tuning only).
- Sensitivity meters. Displays of the sensitivity level for each string.
- Sensitivity increment/decrement buttons. The user can use the arrows to raise or lower the sensitivity setting for each string.
- Sensitivity numerical display. Real time display of the dynamic level of each string, expressed on a scale of 1 to 16, with 16 representing maximum sensitivity.

- MIDI indicator. Lights up when MIDI input is detected.
- Levels/Tuner selector switch. Toggles between Sensitivity and Tuner views.
- Tuner. Displays the current pitch of each string, expressed in cents (hundredths of a half-step)

On the other hand, in order to complete the proposed dataset, score tablature settings have been enabled from logic Pro X. Logic Pro X offers an automatic conversion of notes into tablature, if a staff style containing a Clef parameter is set, these tuning sets are used. The exact characteristics of these tuning sets are determined in the Tablature pane. Moreover, each string information is separately retrieved in different MIDI channels and then converted in finger position information that, finally, determines the tablature, see figure 9.

Figure 9: Score and Tablature excerpt of the recorded performance of There Will Never Be Another You.

In Logic Pro X Score Tablature settings are only available when Additional Score Options is selected in Advanced preferences.

3.2.2 Data Modeling Libraries

Modeling tasks have been the main core of this project and, therefore, in this project, external software libraries have been necessary in order to address several subsections of the modeling task.

As mentioned in the previous sections, the modeling task has been implemented mainly in Jupyter notebook environment, using Colab for expensive computing tasks, therefore, the programming language used is mainly Python.

The actual training and testing of the models are based on the Tensorflow library. TensorFlow is an open source software library released in 2015 by Google to make it easier for developers to design, build, and train deep learning

models. It originated as an internal library that Google developers used to build models in-house. Although TensorFlow is only one of several options available to developers, we choose to use it because of its thoughtful design and ease of use.

The Magenta library offers a tool to work on open source research projects related to machine learning. Magenta is distributed as an open source Python library, powered by TensorFlow⁵. Magenta library includes utilities for manipulating source data (mainly music and images), using this data to train machine learning models, and finally generating new content from these models.

Regarding music, this library offers a wide range of utilities in order to work and manipulate MIDI and Note Sequence information. Magenta also offers trained and pretrained models, in our case PerformanceRNN pretrained models have been reviewed [39]. Magenta library represents the main library used in this project. During the next sections, specific processes where Magenta library is involved are explained.

Although Magenta library is a complete, robust and a recent framework. Some of the utilities needed for this project were not still up to date as expected, even developers from Magenta recognized that some of the features from some specific models are under development and “amazingly” some of them do never worked; e.g., Performance RNN ⁶, therefore, in some situations workarounds have been developed to complete the expected outcome of the project.

Other libraries have been needed in order to store the datasets and the derived trained models, in our case Google Drive has been used. Google Drive is a file storage and synchronization service, developed by Google and for this project it has been used for linking the storage with the Google Colab framework. Therefore, Drive module/library for Google Colab has been also necessary in order to mount and link these two services.

⁵<https://magenta.tensorflow.org/>

⁶<https://github.com/magenta/magenta/issues/768issuecomment-646891355>

3.2.3 Web Application Interface Libraries

The proposed web application is based on html, css and javascript. Most of the functionalities are implemented in javascript and external javascript modules are also imported. In order to interact with the trained model in real-time on the web, magenta.js module is imported.

Magenta.js [40] is a new JavaScript suite with a simple API for generating music and art with Magenta models. Magenta.js is built on Tensorflow.js, therefore, it could run directly in the browser with WebGL-acceleration.

Magenta.js provides a wide range of tools to deal with MIDI and NoteSequence data, it also provides modules focused on the loading and playing processes of MIDI sounds. For example, SoundFont is a module for loading and playing instrument samples. Nevertheless, Magenta.js, as far as is known, does not provide support for the interaction of real instruments connected, therefore, two external libraries have been included, WebMidi.js and Web MIDI API Shim.

WebMidi.js⁷ is an addition to the web platform that allows web developers to interact with MIDI musical instruments and devices.

Web MIDI API Shim⁸ is a javascript library that defines a means for web developers to enumerate, manipulate and access MIDI devices.

3.3 Dataset

The dataset consists of several polyphonic records of guitar performances. In order to obtain reliable results of the proposed project, the dataset is divided into two different styles; Flamenco and Jazz. The aim of this project is focused on flamenco results but jazz style is also acquired for the purpose of comparing approaches.

The dataset has not only been created for this particular project but is meant to be a public resource that can potentially contribute to this research field. Therefore,

⁷<https://github.com/djipco/webmidi>

⁸<https://github.com/cwilso/WebMIDIAPIShim>

extra data has been acquired in order to provide a more comprehensive dataset, i.e. audio and tab data.

As mentioned, the dataset consists of different styles, the data is divided into: one hour based on jazz style and one hour based on flamenco style.

Each set of style contains three kinds of different data, see figure 10:

- MIDI information: MIDI files that contains information about the pitch of the note played, the onset/offset time and the velocity of the note.
- Clean signal: Direct audio signal from the guitar pickup.
- Tablature: Tablature score where performance information and finger position are annotated based on the MIDI information retrieved previously.

Figure 10: MIDI, audio, score and tablature of an excerpt of the recorded performance of *There Will Never Be Another You*.

MIDI is considered the most common symbolic representation of music information. Other approaches use formats such as MUSIC_XML or AbcNotation. MIDI representation is also used as a protocol since it is used to carry note messages that can be used in real-time performance. MIDI messages contains channel information, that indicates the track that the message is sent on. Note number (from 0 to 127) that indicates the pitch of the note and velocity (from 0 to 127) that indicates the

volume of the note. Note On and Note Off messages determine the duration of the notes.

As mentioned before, in this project, only the MIDI information is used, and this MIDI information is then feed to the Magenta pretrained model. For each model in Magenta, MIDI notes are encoded, therefore MIDI format is not used directly in Magenta models, but converted into NoteSequence format. NoteSequences are a protocol buffers (Protobuf) implementation of the musical structure that is then used by TensorFlow. This is somehow hidden from the users since the input and output data is always MIDI. NoteSequence format implementation is useful because it implements a data format available for the training.

Protobuf is a language-neutral, platform-neutral extensible mechanism for serializing structured data. The definition of NoteSequence is based on the content of a MIDI message, which it contains:

- TimeSignature changes: By default, 4/4 is assumed per MIDI standard.
- KeySignature changes: By default, C Major is assumed per MIDI standard.
- Tempo changes: By default, 120 BPM is assumed per MIDI standard.
- A list of Note changes.

Quantization information could also be found, need it for humanization approaches. Moreover, annotations, pitch bend and control changes are included in NoteSequences.

Note list, the main used, includes pitch and start/stop times information. In order to work with NoteSequences format, Magenta library offers several functions to deal with it and with MIDI information.

Converting into and from NoteSequence is essential and instead of hardcoding in Python code, several functions are focused on this, e.g., `note_sequence_to_midi_file` and `midi_file_to_note_sequence`.

Chapter 4

System Overview

The design and implementation of the presented system is divided in three different parts or sections. As mentioned in the previous chapters, the project is divided in the system capable of the acquisition of the dataset, the system responsible for treating the acquired data and then processed and feed to the pre-trained model and finally, the system focused on the implementation and deployment of the web application interface.

In this chapter a review of each system is detailed, and an overall view of the whole framework is also presented.

4.1 Recording System

In the following figure 11, a detailed diagram of the recording system framework is presented. The main core of the system takes place in the DAW Logic Pro X and in the hexaphonic MIDI pickup. As detailed in the diagram, the data is capture by the MIDI pickup and by the audio signal line output of the guitar. The MIDI pickup is connected via a wireless USB and guitar audio line is connected using a jack cable. Both signals are recorded in the same Logic Pro X file and later separated in order to build the mentioned dataset.

Before the recording, both signals have to be adjusted, sensitivity and gain param-

Figure 11: Detailed diagram of the recording system proposed for the project.

eters are calibrated. The sensitivity of the MIDI pickup is adjusted through the TriplePlay software. The line guitar signal gain is adjusted directly in the Focusrite interface. The recorded data is then saved and later converted into the specified data formats; MIDI, tablature and audio.

4.1.1 Recording Sessions and Acquired Data

The dataset retrieved is focused on flamenco, but jazz performances have also been obtained in order to be able to compare the obtained results. For each style, a professional guitarist has participated. The overall size of the dataset is around 2 hours, approximately one of jazz and one of flamenco. Regarding the jazz style performance, the guitarist that participated is a senior student from the “Taller de Músics” from Barcelona. She has more than 10 years of experience as a professional guitarist and closely related with jazz guitar style, although she used to play

pop/rock style, a Gibson ES-339 Custom guitar was used.

On the other hand, the flamenco guitarist that participated had 3 years of experience as a professional flamenco musician but more than 15 year as a guitarist. He has previous knowledge on electric guitar, a fact that helped to deal with playing flamenco style on an electric guitar. An American Fender Stratocaster was used in this session, see figure 12.

Each recording session lasted about two and a half hours, including a break in the middle. During the first 15 minutes, the hexaphonic pickup was installed and tested by the researcher. Then the guitarist tunes the guitar and a signal test (both, MIDI and Audio) is done. Both, the guitarist and the researcher were provided with headphones in order to listened to the output. During the recordings MIDI channel is muted in order to not distract the performer.

For the jazz recording session, backing tracks were used. Each recording includes the follow structure; a melody chorus of the jazz standard, (at least) one chorus of solo and a chorus of the melody again. The guitarist used a pick during the whole performance.

Regarding the flamenco recording session, no backing tracks were used. Each recording includes a whole flamenco performance, and the length of the recordings variate a lot, from one minute to six minutes. No pick was used during the performance. In the following links two videos from the recording sessions are shown comparing the performance between an electric flamenco guitar performance and an acoustic flamenco guitar performance:

Electric guitar performance: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1cC2_jiioIOWq-6K_SipxVY5zHRxu6P72/view?usp=sharing

Acoustic guitar performance: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AC1ESvdJxkAJLMFTon17Nk56z8/view?usp=sharing>

(a) Jazz Recording Session

(b) Flamenco Recording Session

Figure 12: Recording Sessions

4.2 Modeling System

During the following section, an explanation of the system that models the acquired data is shown.

The proposed system is based on Magenta python library, concretely the project is based on PerformanceRNN model. The overall system is represented in the following diagram, figure 13. The system starts with the MIDI files acquired previously. Finally, the results of the system consist on two trained models based on different datasets.

4.2.1 Performance RNN

The core of the system relies on the model used in this project. PerformanceRNN is an LSTM-based recurrent neural network designed to model polyphonic music with expressive timing and dynamics. The model uses a similar MIDI language and it is capable of creating music with note-on and note-off events instead of explicit duration.

The approach in order to deal with expressive timing and dynamics is based on time-shifts events and velocity events. Regarding the expressive timing, the model controls the clock with time-shift events that move forward at increments of 10ms, up to 1 second. On the other hand, the model supports velocity events that set the

Figure 13: Detailed diagram of the modeling system proposed for the project.

current velocity, used by subsequent note-on events.

The model is capable of generating performances with more natural timing and dynamics compared to other Magenta models. These types of approaches led to the GrooVAE model. The generated pieces by PerformanceRNN are not existing ones, the model is capable of choosing the notes to play, “composing” a humanized performance directly.

Expressive timing and dynamics represent an essential part of music and this is one of the main reasons about the use of this model. The dataset used to train the model is the Yamaha e-Piano Competition dataset¹, which contains more than 1400 piano performances. The dataset presents some essential characteristics that fit perfectly in this expressiveness context:

¹<http://www.piano-e-competition.com/>

- Note timings are based on human performances rather than a score.
- Note velocities are based on human performance
- All of the pieces were composed for and performed on one single instrument: piano
- All of the pieces were repertoire selections from a classical piano competition. This implies certain statistical constraints and coherence in the data set.

The first three mentioned-above characteristics can be perfectly applied in the proposed project. The note timings are based on human guitarist performances, the velocities are also based on human performance and all the performed pieces were performed on the same instrument, the guitar. The last characteristic mentioned could imply the need for certain clarifications; all the pieces from the Yamaha dataset were based on the classical piano competition, therefore, statistical constraints and coherence in the results can be too strong to be affected by the fine-tuning of the models.

The performance representation is a MIDI-like stream of musical events. The events used are:

- 28 note-on events, one for each of the 128 MIDI pitches. These events start a new note.
- 128 note-off events, one for each of the 128 MIDI pitches. These events release a note.
- 100 time-shift events in increments of 10 ms up to 1 second. These events move forward in time to the next note event.
- 32 velocity events, corresponding to MIDI velocities quantized into 32 bins. These events change the velocity applied to subsequent notes.

The designed model operates on a one-hot encoding over these 388 different events. 30 second except could contain over 1200 one-hot vectors.

The training process of the PerformanceRNN model contains a pre-processing of the data that is applied in order to create additional training examples, the data is time stretched, (making the performance up to 5% faster or slower) and transposition the pitch by a up to a major third. Each performance is split into 30-second segments to keep each example of manageable size. The model is capable of generate long performances without falling over, though the generated performance has no long-term structure, long performances (around 5 minutes) are possible.

Magenta provides specific information about the PerformanceRNN model, the code is released in the open-source Magenta repository ², along with two pretrained models: one with dynamics and one without. Magenta installation and configuration instructions are provided, and specific information is also available in the book *Hands-On Music Generation with Magenta* [41].

Pretrained models are: “performance”, “performance with dynamics”, “performance with dynamics and modulo encoding”, “density conditioned performance with dynamics”, “pitch conditioned performance with dynamics” and “multiconditioned performance with dynamics”.

The filenames correspond to the configurations defined in the performance model. The first three models use different performance representation. The first, “performance”, ignores note velocities but models note on/off events with expressive timing. The “performance with dynamics” model includes velocity changes quantized into 32 bins. The “performance with dynamics and modulo encoding” model uses an alternate encoding designed by Vida Vakilotojar³ where event values are mapped to points on the unit circle. The last three models are conditional models that can generate performances conditioned on desired note density, desired pitch class distribution, or both, respectively.

For this project the pretrained model is *performance with dynamics* but conditional models are taken into account for future works.

²<https://github.com/magenta/magenta>

³<https://github.com/vidavakil>

4.2.2 PerformanceRNN - Overview of the System

In order to fine-tune a pretrained model, the first step is to convert the collection of acquired MIDI files into a NoteSequence format. NoteSequences, as explained in the previous section, are protocol buffers, which is a fast and efficient data format, and easier to work with than MIDI files. In order to build the proper dataset with the proper format, Magenta provides the instructions to generate a TFRecord (TensorflowRecord) of NoteSequences. The script used is "convert_dir_to_note_sequences", that converts music files to NoteSequence protos and writes TFRecord file. It currently supports MIDI (.mid, .midi) and MusicXML (.xml, .mxl) files.

It receives a string path to the source file relative to the root of the collection as an input and outputs TFRecord file that will contain NoteSequence protocol buffers. The recursive boolean parameter is also set in order to specify whether or not recursively convert files contained in subdirectories of the specified directory.

Once the TFRecord file is created, the model should be feed it with specific TensorFlow's SequenceExample format, therefore, a script is used in order to extract polyphonic tracks from NoteSequence protos and save them to TensorFlow's SequenceExample protos for input to the performance RNN models. It will apply data augmentation, stretching and transposing each NoteSequence within a limited range. Each SequenceExample will contain a sequence of inputs and a sequence of labels that represent a performance.

The script receives as an input the TFRecord file created previously and several parameters, the configuration and the "eval ratio". On the other hand, two outputs of SequenceExamples are generated, one for training, and one for evaluation, where the fraction of SequenceExamples in the evaluation set is determined by "--eval ratio". By default, eval ratio of 0.10 is set, i.e., 10% of the extracted performances will be saved in the eval collection, and 90% will be saved in the training collection.

Consider that the created SequenceExamples must follow the same configuration

as the desired pretrained model, in other words; if the model to be fine-tuned is the “performance with dynamics“, the configuration parameter should match the configuration of the model used when creating the dataset. Moreover, the same configuration should be specified when training the model.

Finally, the last step of the proposed system is the training of the model. For this, Google Colab is used and Tensor Processing Unit (TPU) hardware accelerator is chosen. In order to run the training, the directory where checkpoints and TensorBoard data for the run, is defined. The SequenceExample file, the TFRecord file of SequenceExamples that will be fed to the model, is also received as an input to the training function. Optionally, several parameters can be defined too, e.g., number of training steps: how many update steps to take before exiting the training loop or Hyperparameters.

4.2.3 Workarounds and Fine-Tuning

In this project, "performance with dynamics" pretrained model has been used. The pre-trained models have been provided in a bundle format, a convenient way of combining the model checkpoint, metagraphs and some metadata about the model, into a single file.

Although this is a convenient format, performanceRNN training function ("performance_rnn_train"), only requires specific checkpoints format files to restores the weights, therefore, the bundle file should be converted. Magenta provides a specific script in order to extract a Tensorflow checkpoint from a bundle file ("unpack_bundle").

Nevertheless, even approaching this workaround (and some others), fine-tuning has never worked for RNN Magenta models or has at least been broken for years⁴). An issue has been opened in GitHub regarding the fine-tuning situation, and Magenta developers proposed an in-progress solution that fixes the issue and supports fine-tuning from a bundle file for Performance RNN, i.e., they proposed the adding of

⁴<https://github.com/magenta/magenta/pull/1753>

the ability to fine-tune from bundle file for Performance RNN.

The used function is the same, "performance_rnn_train", but another parameter is included, the "warm_start_bundle_file", that indicates the path to a bundle file that will be used to initialize the model weights for fine-tuning. In the following script, the information of the executed training function is detailed.

```
!python performance_rnn_train.py
--config="performance_with_dynamics"
--sequence_example_file=jazz/training_performances.tfrecord
--warm_start_bundle_file=jazz/performance_with_dynamics.mag
```

The resulting output of the training are the checkpoints, trained models, and the checkpoint metadata used to generate performances.

For each dataset the training time has been approximately 8 hours, performing more than 700 global steps. The approximate accuracy values of the trainings performed are around 80%.

4.3 Web Application System

Once the training is done for all the proposed datasets, an interactive system has been implemented in order to test and play around with the model. The idea is to provide to the user a tool that creates and performs music sequences based on the trained models. The tool has been designed for a non-technology and non-music related user profile; therefore, inputs and outputs tasks are focused to be simple and straightforward, link <https://perf-flamenco-rnn-2.glitch.me/>.

The following section is divided on; the loading of the model, available input entries, running the model and music sequence output, see figure 14.

Figure 14: Detailed diagram of the web Application Interface system proposed for the project.

4.3.1 Loading the Model

TensorFlow.js provides functionality for saving and loading models that have been created with the Layers API or converted from existing TensorFlow models. The models available to be updated can be self-trained models or already trained ones. TensorFlow Javascript models must be identifiable by JSON files, therefore, they provide a model converter in order to convert already trained checkpoints into TensorFlow models that can be used in a web application. The TensorFlow.js converter has two components:

- A command line utility that converts Keras and TensorFlow models for use in TensorFlow.js.
- An API for loading and executing the model in the browser with TensorFlow.js.

The TensorFlow.js converter works with several different model formats: Saved-

Model, Keras model and TensorFlow Hub module. In this project the default format, SavedModel, in which TensorFlow models are saved, is used.

TensorFlow.js converter is an open source library to load a pretrained TensorFlow SavedModel or TensorFlow Hub module into the browser and run inference through TensorFlow.js.

Once the model is converted, a set of weight files and a model topology file is created. TensorFlow.js provides model loading APIs that can be used to fetch these model assets and run inference in the browser.

The model has been successfully uploaded and initialized but an error appeared when trying the method *continueSequence* in order to generate new sequences. A github report-issue has opened to ask to support or any workaround⁵. Magenta developers clarify that there is currently no PerformanceRNN data converter for use with MusicRNN, therefore, the model cannot be easily implemented in the web application but they suggest to adapt the, totally separated, Performance RNN JS demo codebase⁶ to work with my checkpoint. This approach is now considered as a future work and consequently, the web application is not fully developed at the moment.

4.3.2 Web Application Inputs

Several input entries are available for the user in order to create or upload music excerpts for the model input. Nevertheless, each input will be converted into Note-Sequence format to facilitate the manipulation and compatibility with the running of the model.

The web application interface provides three different types of inputs; an *interactive MIDI panel*, the *uploading of MIDI files* and the *live performing and recording using external MIDI instruments*.

⁵<https://github.com/magenta/magenta-js/issues/26>

⁶https://github.com/magenta/magenta-demos/tree/master/performance_rnn

Interactive MIDI Panel

The implemented MIDI panel is provided with an interactive pixel board with a pitch range of 24 notes, (24 “pixels”) and 32 timesteps. The range of the pitches of the interactive MIDI panel go from 48 to 72 MIDI notes. Each pixel represents a note in a specific timestep, and it can be activated or deactivated.

Once the user creates the sequence, it can be played; a "clear" button is also provided in order to remove all the activated "pixels" of the board. A range slide is implemented in order to change the tempo of the created sequence. Once the user finishes the creation of a melody using the MIDI panel, the user would select a model and run it using the input sequence, see figure 15.

Figure 15: Interactive MIDI panel implemented in the Web Application, work in progress.

Upload MIDI File

In order to interact with the model, the user can directly upload MIDI files into the web application. The MIDI information uploaded is then updated on the MIDI panel and in a score canvas section on the bottom of the page.

Then the user can modify the uploaded MIDI information through the panel and then run the model with the modified information or, on the other hand, directly run the model using the updated score canvas information, figure 16. Tempo can be also modified using the range slide.

Figure 16: Canvas Frame implemented in order to print and play the uploaded MIDI file, work in progress.

Recording MIDI information

A third input method has been implemented. An input of live recording is provided for those users that are used to use MIDI devices.

The web application provides a toggle selector of the MIDI inputs available detected; e.g., keyboard, MIDI pickups or virtual MIDI inputs (IAC Driver BUS). Once the desired input device is selected the user can start recording the input melody for the model. A stop button is provided and can be pressed whenever it is needed. The recorded sequences are then uploaded into the MIDI panel so the user can still modify some notes before running the model, figure 17.

Figure 17: MIDI buttons section; used to play and stop recordings and playback sequences, upload a MIDI file and a range slider to change tempo. Toggle selector in order to select the detected input devices (e.g., IAC Driver Bus 1), work in progress.

Running the Model and Output Sequence

As mentioned before the complete implementation of the model in the web application is not developed yet due to the uncompleted developments of the Magenta Team. The desired behavior of this part is the following;

- The user is capable of selecting which model want to use (Jazz-based or Flamenco-based) on the created or uploaded sequence.
- The user is able of selecting the temperature of the the model, i.e., the randomness of the samples. Decreasing the temperature value reduces the randomness of the event distribution, which can make performances sound repetitive. For small decreases this may be an improvement, as some repetition is natural in music.
- The model generate one output based on the input sequence and the temperature value.
- The generated sequence is printed on a score canvas. The user can play the output sequence and change the tempo. By pressing the download button, the generated sequence can be downloaded and saved as a MIDI file.

Chapter 5

Results

Currently, the integration of the model in the web application is not implemented.

In the following chapter we analyse the main results involved on the data acquisition system, the performance of the models and the perceptual quality tests.

5.1 Acquisition System Results

Regarding the acquisition system, the data obtained can be directly used by the model. The recordings must start just before the performer starts playing, thus, no empty space in the first seconds is processed by the model. Similarly, the recordings should stop just after the performer finished. With these two points in mind, the data is clean enough and it can be used directly by the model, observe the following examples and comparison between the MIDI and Audio data retrieved.

MIDI Audio Track: <https://tinyurl.com/y2qcelu7>

Line Audio Track: <https://tinyurl.com/y44oc4p7>

5.2 Model Performance

Several training sessions have been performed using two different datasets, on one hand a guitar jazz dataset and on the other hand a flamenco dataset. Nevertheless,

Training Session	Hardware Accelerator	Steps	Time	Loss	Accuracy	Training Set	Over-fitting
1	TPU	1095	7h 22 min	0,16	0,98	Jazz	YES
2	TPU	561	7h 12 min	0,83	0,76	Flamenco	YES
3	GPU	1000	41min	0,25	0,91	Jazz	NO
4	GPU	1000	41min	0,25	0,91	Flamenco	NO

Table 1: Specifications related with some of the training sessions performed.

a third dataset has been used in order to test the framework and the environment before training it with the recorded dataset, this dataset is based on New Orleans jazz melodies, retrieved from the MIDI files from the following website: <http://www.angelpig.com/midis.html>.

During the first training sessions it has been detected that the model probably over-fits, during those sessions TPU hardware accelerator was used. Therefore, several other training sessions have been performed with a fix number of steps, the following table summarize the obtained values of these sessions, table 1.

The following graphs summarizes some of the values got on some of the training sessions, figure ??.

(a) Plot of the jazz loss training, GPU was used. (b) Plot of the flamenco loss training, GPU was used.

Moreover, GPU hardware acceleration shown faster results and has been used to get several results with an specific number of iterations. As mentioned, the optimum results are around 1K iterations for GPU, about 40 minutes, getting 91% accuracy.

In order to get all the metrics, TensorBoard in Colab has been used, and a script

Track	Mono / Poly	URL
AI_Jazz_01	Mostly Monophonic	https://tinyurl.com/y5yxm7uf
AI_Jazz_02	Monophonic	https://tinyurl.com/yxapmttt
AI_Jazz_03	Polyphonic	https://tinyurl.com/y5w5hsj6
AI_Flamenco_01	Polyphonic	https://tinyurl.com/y3dc2va9
AI_Flamenco_02	Polyphonic	https://tinyurl.com/yypvrzrf
AI_Flamenco_03	Polyphonic	https://tinyurl.com/y323xdgb

Table 2: Online examples of the generated excerpts.

has been implemented in order to save the data in Pandas DataFrames.

A first batch of results has been computed in order to run several perceptual experiments, 10 output sequences were generated. In order to generate the output sequences a seed excerpt is needed. For all the outputs generated, the seeds used are the Fur Elisa and the 5th Symphony, by Beethoven.

In the following table we can find several demos of the output sequences, table 2.

As we can observe, in the TPU sessions, over-fitting is present and some of the sequences from the dataset are exactly replicated on the output sequences.

5.3 Perceptual Melody Tests

In order to get a qualitative results, two perceptual online test on the generated sequences has been performed. Both of them has been created using Google Forms and the music excerpts were uploaded in Google Drive. The first test was focused on the style differentiation between the excerpts created, i.e., if the user can differentiate between an AI flamenco generated excerpt and an AI jazz generated excerpt. A second survey has been generated in order to see if the user is capable of differentiate between real excerpts and AI generated excerpts, this survey is divided into two parts one focused on each style.

A total of 20 excerpts has been created for the style differentiation survey, 10 songs generated by the model trained with the jazz dataset and the other 10 generated by the model trained with the flamenco dataset.

As a primer input midi file (seed), two different classical music excerpts, have been used; an excerpt of 4 seconds from Beethoven's Fur Elisa and an excerpt of 4 seconds from Beethoven's 5th Symphony. Future tests regarding primer input sequences are planned. The difference between primer inputs is barely noticeable.

The resulting excerpts have 3000 steps, each step is 10ms long, therefore, the duration of each excerpt is 30 seconds.

5.3.1 Style Differentiation Survey

The participants are briefly introduced to the survey, explaining that the following excerpts were created by an Artificial Intelligence system. The survey consists on 20 questions where the participants have to decide if the songs is more related to Jazz or Flamenco, see figure 19. Some previous knowledge related to this music styles is preferred in order to be able to answer the survey properly, therefore, a question regarding how familiarized the participant to those styles is, is asked, see figure 20.

Performance RNN - Flamenco Jazz - Survey

Classify the following music excerpt:
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/10KQMGnTG7h5RmVFUuXqr-lzZ3UHYVyzj/view?usp=sharing> *

Flamenco

Jazz

Cannot be classified

Figure 19: Example of one of the questions asked in the style survey.

From each music excerpt a subexcerpt has been manually selected following the researcher criteria. This music subexcerpts selected have a length around 5-10 seconds in order to answer a straightforward survey, preferably, musical melodies and musical repetitions are selected. A guitar plugin has been used in order to create a natural sound related with the related music instrument used.

Url of the survey; <https://forms.gle/7qUGB2RkfrEDxvAG9>

Have you ever listened to jazz music? *

Yes

No

Have you ever listened to flamenco music? *

Yes

No

Figure 20: Question asked in the style survey regarding previous knowledge related to styles.

5.3.2 Human vs. AI Survey

We built two different surveys, one focused on the jazz style, the other on flamenco. Again, the participants are briefly introduced to the survey. In this case, we explain that half of the excerpts that are going to listen are generated by an AI. The survey consists on 10 questions where the participants have to decide how much human-generated or AI-generated the listened excerpt is perceived. possible answer is between 1 to 5, being 1 human-generated and 5 AI-generated, see figure 21.

From 1 to 5 classify the following excerpt, 1 is Human-generated, 5 is AI-generated. Audio: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1YkLPnk2CW5I-8Wwz-2HwkBG3zZaEQzDN/view?usp=sharing> *

1 2 3 4 5

Human-generated AI-generated

Figure 21: Example of one of the questions asked in the Human vs. AI survey.

As before, from each music excerpt a subexcerpt (5-10 seconds) has been manually selected following the researcher criteria. A guitar plugin has been used in order to create a more natural sound related with the instrument used during the acquisition

process, the guitar.

Url of the survey, Flamenco; <https://forms.gle/APR2i1R76wD698Xh6>

Url of the survey, Jazz; <https://forms.gle/aqeLEgRuCzwEC1EV6>

5.3.3 Dynamics

Another important result to take into account of the researched project is focused on the acquisition of dynamics information and the modeling of them. As mentioned during the previous sections, dynamics information is an interested feature to acquire by the hexaphonic MIDI pickup and therefore, check if the retrieved information is modeled by the training, and, moreover, two types of dynamics would be distinguished by the proposed styles.

The last questions proposed in the "Style Differentiation Survey" is related to this topic, and it asks regarding the importance of the dynamics in the listened music excerpts, see figure 22.

The image shows a survey question titled "Dynamics" in a purple header. The question text is: "From 1 to 5, Do you think that dynamics represent an important role in the listened excerpts? (5 a lot, 1 not that much)". Below the text are five radio button options labeled 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 22: Question regarding dynamics in the style differentiation survey.

Chapter 6

Discussion

The project described presents a complex system based on three main parts; The data acquisition, the modeling of the data acquired and the interactive web application.

Regarding the first part, the data acquisition system has proven to be a reliable system in order to acquire polyphonic guitar performance data that involves expressiveness information too. The system is affordable, non-intrusive and straightforward to use. If the recording session is monitored, the data acquired by the system is clean and ready to use. For this project, no data-cleaning pre-processing has been used. Therefore, this system could be ideal for reliable and efficient guitar performance data acquisition tasks.

However, as mentioned in the previous sections, the system is specific for electric guitars. It could be possible to acquire data from other types of guitars but may not be clean enough to use it without processing it.

Related to this; the flamenco style is not used to be played on an electric guitar, nevertheless, in this project we proved that the acquired information by the proposed system is still valid for flamenco modeling purposes.

The proposed system is capable of acquiring, not only pitch information of each string, but expressiveness information regarding the performance. In the presented

work, the expressiveness information refers, mainly, to the particular velocities (intensity) of the played notes, in each particular style.

The proposed work focuses on the performance generation and we do not take into account specific expressiveness features of a specific style. We do consider expressiveness features that we might find in a music sequence, but we do not model the feature itself, but modeled sequences containing these features (because we were able to acquire them).

On the other hand, the presented project focuses on the modeling of flamenco and jazz guitar performances, that contain expressiveness information (specific in each style), in order to generate music sequence excerpts. Therefore, the resulting automatic generated excerpts, will contain expressiveness information related to each of these styles.

Regarding the modeling, the results obtained shown that the generated sequences can be easily differentiated between jazz and flamenco. The survey is still in progress but at the moment 25 participants have answered it and 80% of the classifications are correctly done. The 85,7% of the participants think that dynamics represent an important role in the music excerpts listened. This results prove that the generated sounds are distinguishable between styles.

On the other hand, we have tested if the sequences can be also differentiate between human-generated sequences and AI-generated ones.

Regarding the jazz style, the results shown that 19.6% of the excerpts cannot be differentiate between human-generated and AI-generated (3/5 score). The 27.2% of the excerpts were classified correctly; maximum score.

44.4% of the excerpts were classified as the expected group but not with the maximum score, 2/5 score in Human and 4/5 score in AI. 8.8% of the excerpts were misclassified.

The results regarding the jazz tests, shown that human and AI excerpts can be generally distinguished but participants were not sure enough in order to rank them with

the maximum score. As observed in the figure 23, therefore, somehow, AI-generated excerpts can be mistaken for human-generated ones, but we cannot consider the results completely reliable as the number of participants is not sufficient. However, we may expect similar scores and therefore a room for improvements.

Figure 23: Diagram of the general results of the perception tests.

In the case of flamenco style, the results shown that almost 30% (28,80%) of the excerpts cannot be classified, 3/5 score. The 31,60% of the excerpts were wrongly classified, only a 6,80% of the excerpts were correctly classified with the highest score. The rest, the 32,80% of the excerpts, were classified correctly but not rated with the highest possible score; 2/5 in the case of the Human-generated excerpts and 4/5 in the case of the AI-generated excerpts.

As seen in the diagram 23, these results shown that the distinction between groups is not clear, therefore, we could conclude that flamenco AI-generated excerpts could be perceived as human-generated ones. However, as mentioned before, 25 participants i.e., 250 excerpts, is not a reliable amount, but we could expect similar scores if more tests are performed.

Figure 24 and figure 25 show the mean of the scores of each excerpt. Other figures related to the individual results of each extract are attached in the appendix, see Appendix A.

Other aspects to take into account regarding the jazz dataset are that the recorded excerpts contain parts of monophonic guitar solos, thus the model has been influ-

Figure 24: Mean score of each excerpt, jazz style.

Figure 25: Mean score of each excerpt, flamenco style.

enced by this, generating mostly monophonic sequences.

In the case of flamenco, the music recorded was complex, i.e., all the dataset acquired was polyphonic and most of the time all the strings were strummed at the same time. This could potentially involve in the complexity of the modeling increasing the difficulty, considering only one hour of recorded data. Although the data recorded was complex, it was successfully acquired and the model generated some interesting guitar flamenco excerpts; excerpts that have been considered as human-generated.

Regarding the web application, as mentioned in the previous sessions, it cannot be finished yet. However, the proposed application showed to be a useful tool in order

to generate music excerpts for later interaction with the model.

6.1 Future Work

The presented work shown interesting results that we believe that can be relevant for future work directions. However, some work could be improved in order to have more reliable results. Moreover, one of the main purposes of the presented project relies on the interactive web application tool capable of generating new conditioned-AI sequences. As mentioned in the previous sections, the web application is not finished yet and we propose the implementation of the model on the web application as a future work.

We believe that is crucial to provide a tool to the stakeholders in order to interact with the trained models. Interested users may not always be acquainted with the technology or music fields, therefore we proposed the web application as a simple interactive real-time tool. We also propose usability tests on the web application interface to confirm the complexity in non experienced users.

Regarding the trained models, we observed that more data could improve the results, especially in the flamenco style, although it . We also observed that the jazz acquired data contains a considerable part of monophonic data. We propose the acquisition of more data of both styles.

Finally, as observed in the attached videos of the recordings¹, a lot of percussive information is lost in guitar flamenco performances. We propose a system based on a piezoelectric microphone to capture percussive information for the later modeling.

6.2 Reproducibility

The following google drive folder contains: the Jupyter notebook in order to train the model, some examples generated using the trained model, two checkpoints; one trained for flamenco style and one for jazz style. It also contains part of the dataset

¹https://drive.google.com/file/d/1cC2_jiioI0Wq-6K_SipxVY5zHRxu6P72/view?usp=sharing

acquired and used in this work. In the folder there is also visual documentation regarding the recording sessions.

Link: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1zY2QP99c78wRX42cG3zTrVF1QbVLKnsp?usp=sharing>

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Appendix A

Test Results

Figure 26: Results of the perception tests on flamenco style excerpts part 1, scores and participants. Score: AI-generated = 1, Human-generated = 5.

Figure 27: Results of the perception tests on flamenco style excerpts part 2, scores and participants. Score: AI-generated = 1, Human-generated = 5.

Figure 28: Results of the perception tests on jazz style excerpts part 1, scores and participants. Score: AI-generated = 1, Human-generated = 5.

Figure 29: Results of the perception tests on jazz style excerpts part 2, scores and participants. Score: AI-generated = 1, Human-generated = 5.